

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Base Hydrolysis of Chloro- and Bromo(*N*-(2-pyridinylmethylene)-*N'*-[3-[2-pyridinylmethylene]amino]propyl]-1,3-propanediamine)cobalt(III), [CoLX]²⁺

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Complexes [CoLX]²⁺ (X = Cl, Br) contain a single acidic proton and the site of conjugate base formation is thus defined. These complexes undergo extremely rapid base hydrolysis with $k_{OH^-} = 1.83 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (X = Cl) and $k_{OH^-} = 3.5 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (X = Br) at 25°. The corresponding activation parameters are $\Delta H^\ddagger = 50.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger_{900} = +43 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (X = Cl) and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 49.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger_{900} = +45 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Base hydrolysis of the chloro complex is subject to general base catalysis by OAc⁻ indicating that rate determining proton transfer occurs in the base hydrolysis reaction.

The great sensitivity of cobalt(III) amine complexes towards base hydrolysis stands in marked contrast to the much weaker effects observed with other metal centres¹. The base catalysed substitution process requires deprotonation of a suitably located amine group, either rapidly and reversibly or in certain circumstances, rate limiting to give an amido species which is substitutionally labile (1-3),

For complexes of some unsaturated multidentate ligands such as *N*-(2-pyridinylmethylene)-*N'*-[3-[2-pyridinylmethylene]amino]propyl]-1,3-propanediamine (1=L) only a single site for deprotonation exists.

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Although complexes [CoLX]²⁺ can occur as four geometrical isomers (2-5), preparations using cobalt(II) and the ligand as precursors give a single geometrical isomer, which has been identified by ¹H nmr as 5.

Results and Discussion

Complexes [CoLX](ClO₄)₂ (X = Cl, Br, NO₂, N₃) have been prepared and characterised. Analytical and conductivity data is summarised in Table 1. The complexes are highly crystalline and range in colour from pinkish red to dark brown. They are soluble in water and nitromethane but are only moderately soluble in methanol and ethanol. The conductivity of nitromethane solutions confirms that all of the complexes behave as 2 : 1 electrolytes in this solvent.

Infrared data is summarised in Table 1. The C=N stretching vibration occurs in the region 1 615-1 620 cm⁻¹ in the cobalt(II) complexes compared with 1 644 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand. A medium to weak band which is quite sharp in the range 3 180-3 220 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the NH stretching mode. The sharpness of the band excludes extensive hydrogen bonding in the solid state. In pyridine metal complexes, four ring

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA FOR COBALT(III) COMPLEXES OF pyDPT

Compd. (Colour)	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)			$\Delta M^*/$ $S\ cm^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$	$\lambda_{max},\ nm/$ $(\epsilon,\ M^{-1}\ cm^{-1})$	NH C=N		$\nu_{max}^{**}\ (cm^{-1})$			
	C	H	N					Pyridine ring			
								I,	II,	III,	IV
[Co(pyDPT)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂ (Reddish pink)	35.92 (35.87)	3.78 (3.85)	11.54 (11.62)	170 (2:1)	539(73), 435(51) ^a	3 200	1 644	1 587,	1 567,	1 468,	1 435
[Co(pyDPT)Br](ClO ₄) ₂ (Brown)	32.76 (33.41)	3.52 (3.58)	11.02 (10.81)	164 (2:1)	550(55) ^b	3 100	1 615	1 590,	1 580,	1 480,	1 440
[Co(pyDPT)NO ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (Orange yellow)	35.20 (35.25)	3.56 (3.78)	13.88 (13.70)	159 (2:1)	502	3 000	1 615	1 590,	1 575,	1 470,	Band obscured by ν_{NO_2}
[Co(pyDPT)N](ClO ₄) ₂ (Rusty brown)	35.17 (35.48)	3.40 (3.81)	18.64 (18.39)	173 (2:1)	460	3 100	1 615	1 600,	1 580,	1 470,	1 435

*Conductivities obtained using 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solution of the complexes in CH₃NO₂ at 25°. For a 1:1 electrolyte, $\Delta_M = 85-97\ S\ cm^2\ mol^{-1}$, and for a 2:1 electrolyte, $\Delta_M = 177\ S\ cm^2\ mol^{-1}$ (N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3999). **pyDPT ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 644 (C=N); Pyridine ring bands 1 587(I), 1 567(II), 1 468(III) and 1 435 cm⁻¹(IV). ^aIn 1 M HCl. ^b1 M HBr.

Fig. 1. Interval scan spectrum for base hydrolysis of [CoLBr](ClO₄)₃ in succinate buffer (pH 4.61) at 25° and $I=0.1\ mol\ dm^{-3}$ (KNO₃). The time interval between scans is 30 s.

vibrations are normally observed around 1 600, 1 590, 1 480 and 1 440 cm^{-1} . This basic pattern is observed in the present complexes.

The visible spectra of the cobalt(III) complexes are summarised in Table 1. The two observable electronic transitions for the cobalt(III) ion in an octahedral field are seen in the chloro complex with the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition at 539 nm ($\epsilon = 78 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ at 435 nm ($\epsilon = 51 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In the bromo, azido and nitro complexes the high energy ligand field band is masked by the charge transfer transition.

Base hydrolysis: The kinetics of base hydrolysis of $[\text{CoLX}]^{2+}$ (X=Cl, Br) were monitored spectrophotometrically. Base hydrolysis is extremely rapid, and it was necessary to study the reaction using succinate buffers with $\text{pH} < 6$.

The interval scan spectrum for the hydrolysis of $[\text{CoLBr}]^{2+}$ in succinate buffer at $\text{pH} 4.61$ is shown in Fig. 1. As hydrolysis occurs the absorption bands move to lower wavelength as the hydroxo ligand exerts a stronger ligand field than bromide. Isosbestic points are maintained throughout the entire reaction (X=Cl at 460 and 530 nm; X=Br at 450 and 520 nm).

The hydrolysis was monitored at 480 nm for the chloro complex and at 560 nm for the bromo complex. An absorbance increase occurs with the chloro complex and an absorbance decrease with the bromo complex. Values of k_{obs} (the observed first order rate constant at constant pH) show a first order dependence on the hydroxide ion concentration with $k_{\text{OH}} = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{OH}^-]$. The base hydrolysis of both the complexes was studied in the pH range 3.8–5.8 over the temperature range 25–40°. The kinetic data obtained are summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

The temperature dependence of k_{OH} for the chloro complex gives $\Delta H^\ddagger = 50.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger_{298} = 43.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The corresponding parameters for the bromo complex are $\Delta H^\ddagger = 49.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger_{298} = 45.3 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. At 25°, the rate constants k_{OH} are 1.83×10^6 (X=Cl) and $3.5 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (X=Br). Base hydrolysis of $[\text{CoLCl}]^{2+}$ is some 10^6 fold faster than $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ at 25°. For the latter complex $k_{\text{OH}} = 0.81 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with $\Delta H^\ddagger = 120 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger_{298} = 155 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

It is now well established that the rapid base hydrolysis of acidoamine cobalt(III) complexes is due to the generation of a dissociatively labile amido species. Hendersen and Tobe³ discussed various factors which influence the reactivity of cobalt(III) complexes in base hydrolysis. Deprotonation takes place at a nitrogen atom which is the middle member of a meridional set of three donors (called 'flat' for convenience). The requirements for high reactivity in base hydrolysis can be summarised: (i) there should be a flat secondary nitrogen to form the amido group, (ii) the amido group should be *cis* to the leaving group and (iii) the plane of the amido group in the intermediate should be able

 TABLE 2—BASE HYDROLYSIS OF $[\text{Co}(\text{pyDPT})\text{Cl}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ IN AQUEOUS SUCCINATE BUFFERS

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{KNO}_3)$				
Temp. °C	pH	$10^6 [\text{OH}^-]^a$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}^b$ s^{-1}	$10^{-6} k_{\text{OH}}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
25	3.91	0.101	0.191	1.89
	4.10	0.165	0.301	1.82
	4.29	0.253	0.416	1.66
	4.49	0.422	0.784	1.85
	4.63	0.621	1.162	1.87
	5.32	2.637	5.342	1.98
	5.75	7.343	12.841	1.75
27	3.91	0.123	0.255	2.07
	4.10	0.191	0.385	2.02
	4.29	0.296	0.568	1.92
	4.48	0.458	0.984	2.15
	4.68	0.727	1.512	2.07
	5.32	3.170	6.781	2.14
	5.75	8.530	17.314	2.03
30	3.86	0.139	0.370	2.66
	4.09	0.235	0.549	2.34
	4.26	0.350	0.950	2.74
	4.49	0.591	1.583	2.68
	4.69	0.945	2.547	2.69
	5.43	5.135	13.821	2.68
	5.89	15.049	36.752	2.34
40	3.81	0.241	1.352	5.61
	3.42	0.479	2.250	4.70
	4.73	0.760	4.021	5.28
	4.51	1.212	6.324	5.22
	4.70	1.914	8.241	4.30

^aCalculated from standard values of γ_{\pm} , $\text{p}K_{\text{W}}$ at each temperature. ^bAverage of three independent runs. $\Delta H^\ddagger = 50.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; $\Delta S^\ddagger_{298} = 43.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

 TABLE 3—BASE HYDROLYSIS OF $[\text{Co}(\text{pyDPT})\text{Br}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ IN AQUEOUS SUCCINATE BUFFERS

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{KNO}_3)$				
Temp. °C	pH	$10^6 [\text{OH}^-]^a$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}^b$ s^{-1}	$10^{-6} k_{\text{OH}}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
25	4.03	0.140	0.511	3.65
	4.22	0.217	0.753	3.47
	4.40	0.328	1.191	3.63
	4.61	0.532	1.920	3.61
	4.98	1.247	4.502	3.45
	5.14	1.802	6.181	3.43
30	4.03	0.204	1.016	4.98
	4.22	0.317	1.600	5.05
	4.40	0.479	2.352	4.91
	4.61	0.777	3.831	4.93
	4.98	1.822	9.292	5.10
	5.14	2.633	13.139	4.99
35	4.03	0.291	2.031	6.98
	4.22	0.451	3.143	6.97
	4.40	0.683	4.856	7.11
	4.61	1.011	6.844	6.77
	4.98	2.597	18.179	7.00
	5.14	3.745	25.466	6.80
40	3.82	0.252	2.452	9.73
	4.03	0.408	4.002	9.81
	4.22	0.632	6.333	10.02
	4.40	0.957	8.966	9.40
	4.61	1.552	14.573	9.39
	4.98	3.639	34.898	9.59
5.14	5.260	49.44	9.40	

^aCalculated from standard values of γ_{\pm} , $\text{p}K_{\text{W}}$ at each temperature. ^bAverage of three independent runs. $\Delta H^\ddagger = 49.14 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; $\Delta S^\ddagger_{298} = 45.3 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

to lie perpendicular to the trigonal plane of cobalt. The complexes $[\text{CoLX}]^{2+}$ satisfy these requirements as the single acidic proton is in the centre of a mer configuration and lies *cis* to the leaving group X. The structure of some related chloropentamine complexes and rate constants k_{OH} for base hydrolysis are summarised in Fig. 2. The *fac-fac* stereochemistry in $\alpha\alpha$ - $[\text{Co}(\text{tetren})\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ leads to quite slow hydrolysis while the mer arrangements in $(\text{CoCl}(\text{pn})(\text{dien}))^{2+}$, $\alpha\beta\text{R}$ - $[\text{CoCl}(\text{tetren})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{CoCl}(\text{[16]aneN}_5)]^{2+}$ lead to rapid base hydrolysis⁴.

Fig. 2. Base hydrolysis rates at 25° and structures of various chloropentamine complexes.

In the S_N1(CB) mechanism loss of the leaving group X is normally rate-determining, however in recent years a number of examples of general base catalysis have been described⁵. The general reaction scheme can be summarised¹.

For general base catalysis to be observed $k_2 \gg k_{-1}[\text{BH}^+]$, where B is any base in solution. If k_{obs} is the observed first order rate constant at constant pH, the rate expression is given by

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{aq}} + k_{\text{OH}}[\text{OH}^-] + k_3[\text{B}]$$

where, k_{aq} is the first order rate constant for aquation and k_3 the second order rate constant for general base catalysis. The observation of general base catalysis rather than specific base catalysis is consistent with rate-determining proton transfer in which deprotonation of AH becomes rate-determining. In order to determine if general base catalysis occurred in the present reactions, base hydrolysis was studied in a series of buffer solutions of constant buffer ratio and ionic strength, but varying the total buffer concentration.

Typical data for the base hydrolysis of $[\text{CoLCl}]^{2+}$ at 25° is shown in Fig. 3. As the buffer concentration is increased the values of k_{obs} increase, and the slope of the line gives $k_{\text{OAc}} = 1.86 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°. The reaction is subject to general

Fig. 3. Plot of k_{obs} vs acetate concentration for the base hydrolysis of $[\text{CoLCl}]^{2+}$ at 25°.

base catalysis and deprotonation of the complex is the rate-determining step. As an approximate guide, cobalt(III) complexes having base hydrolysis rates with k_{OH} greater than $5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are subject to general base catalysis. In addition, these reactions display relatively 'low' values of ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger . For S_N1(CB) reactions the estimated value of ΔS^\ddagger is ca. $+140 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ with ΔH^\ddagger ca. 100 kJ mol^{-1} . In cases where proton transfer becomes rate-determining ΔH^\ddagger is 50–70 kJ mol^{-1} with low positive values of ΔS^\ddagger of +33 to +70 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ ⁶. The activation parameters obtained for the present complexes are fully in accord with these observations. A dependence on the leaving group is also observed with $k_{\text{OH}}(\text{Br})/k_{\text{OH}}(\text{Cl}) = 1.9$.

Labilisation by the heterocyclic nitrogen: Tobe¹ pointed out that pyridine complexes present 'something of a puzzle'. In aquation reactions, ammonia,

primary amines and heterocyclic amines have similar labilising effects, however, in base hydrolysis the heterocyclic ligand labilises the leaving group some 10^2 to 10^3 times more effectively than the other amines. For example, for the base hydrolysis of *cis*-[CoCl(en)₂py]²⁺ and *cis*-[CoCl(en)₂NH₂Me]²⁺ the rate constants k_{OH} are 1.6×10^3 and $12.8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25° and $I=0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. It has been suggested that the heterocyclic nitrogen atom of pyridine can function as a π -electron pair donor by addition of hydroxide at the α -carbon atom in a pseudo-base mechanism (Scheme 1). However, this view is inconsistent with a deuterium isotope study⁶, in which it was shown that *cis*-[CoCl(en)₂py]²⁺ and *cis*-[CoCl(en)₂(²H₆-py)]²⁺ undergo base hydrolysis at the same rate. A deuterium isotope effect would be expected if the pseudo-base mechanism applied.

Scheme 1

Table 4 summarises values of k_{OH} for complexes where pyridine is present either as a monodentate or as part of a multidentate ligand system. These rate constants are compared with those for analogous complexes where pyridine is replaced by NH₃, NH₂ or >NH.

TABLE 4—SOME EXAMPLES OF THE LABILISING EFFECT OF A PYRIDYL GROUP

Compd.*	$10^{-4}/k_{OH}^{**}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	$k_{OH}^{py}/k_{OH}^{NH_3}$
α - <i>cis</i> -[Co(picen)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^a	0.11	16
α - <i>cis</i> -[Co(rien)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^a	0.007	
β - <i>cis</i> -[Co(pictn)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^a	210	78
β - <i>cis</i> -[Co(2,3,2-tet)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^b	2.7	
<i>syn</i> - α - β -[Co(picdien)Cl] ²⁺ ^c	1980	570
<i>syn</i> - α - β -[Co(tetren)Cl] ²⁺ ^c	3.5	
<i>mer</i> -[Co(bmp)(en)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^d	0.77	0.015
<i>mer</i> -[Co(dien)(en)Cl ₂] ²⁺ ^e	50.0	

*picdien=1,9-bis(2'-pyridyl)-2,5,8-triazanonane; for further details of these reactions see E. AHMED, C. CHATTERJEE, C. J. COOKSBY, M. L. TOBE, G. WILLIAMS and M. HUMANES, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 645.

**At 25°. ^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 8. ^cRef. 9. ^dRef. 10. ^eRef. 11.

Significant rate enhancements are observed in the pyridine derivatives. An apparent exception

lies in the comparison of the unsymmetrical *mer*-[Co(bamp)(tn)Cl]²⁺ with [Co(dien)(tn)Cl]²⁺, (bamp=2,6-bis(aminomethyl)pyridine, tn=1,3-diaminopropane) where the pyridine complex is less reactive. This observation demonstrates the high labilising power of the 'flat' *sec*-NH when it is *cis* to the leaving group. In bamp the 'flat' *sec*-NH is replaced by pyridine. This observation supports the view that the pyridyl group does not function as an efficient alternative π -donor.

Experimental

[Co(pyDPT)Cl](ClO₄)₂: To a stirred solution of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (5.35 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in methanol (50 cm³) containing triethylorthoformate (3 cm³) was added 1,7-diamino-4-azahexane (3.28 g, 0.025 mol). The solution was then gently refluxed for 30 min when a colour change from pale yellow to orange was observed. A solution of CoCl₂·6H₂O (5.45 g, 0.025 mol) in methanol (100 cm³) was then added and air bubbled through the solution for 1 h. Solid LiClO₄ was added with stirring until precipitation began. After cooling in an ice-bath the red precipitate was dried. The crude complex was dissolved in the minimum volume of HCl (1 M; ca. 60°), filtered and solid NaClO₄ added with stirring until precipitation began. After cooling the resulting crystals were washed with ethanol then diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure (yield 7.12 g). In 1 M HCl the complex had λ_{max} 539 nm ($\epsilon=78 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 453 nm ($\epsilon=51$).

[Co(pyDPT)Br](ClO₄)₂: It was prepared essentially as described above replacing cobalt(III) chloride by cobalt(III) bromide hexahydrate (8.05 g, 0.025 mol) in methanol (100 cm³). After aeration for 1 h, concentrated HBr (20 cm³) was added to the solution which deepened to a dark brown causing precipitation of a dark brown complex. It was immediately converted to the perchlorate salt by further dilution with methanol and addition of sodium perchlorate. The shiny dark brown crystals were dried and dissolved in a minimum volume of warm methanol with stirring. Cooling in ice gave the dark brown complex (yield 7.2 g). In 1 M HBr the complex had λ_{max} 550 nm ($\epsilon=55 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

[Co(pyDPT)NO₂](ClO₄)₂: The chloro-complex was dissolved in the minimum volume of water and an equivalent amount of NaNO₂ added. The solution was heated on a steam-bath for 30 min and the colour of the solution rapidly changed from wine-red to yellow-orange. The resulting yellow crystals separated on cooling to room temperature, were washed with cold water, followed by ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure (yield 90%).

[Co(pyDPT)N₃](ClO₄)₂: The chloro-complex (2 g) was dissolved in a 4 M solution of sodium azide and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for ~1 h. A colour change from wine red to dark brown was observed. The brown crystals formed on

cooling, were washed with cold water, ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure (yield 90%).

Infrared spectra (KBr) were determined using a Shimadzu-435 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 5 spectrophotometer. All pH measurements were made using a Radiometer PHM 26 Research pH meter standardised with the appropriate NBS buffers.

The kinetics of base hydrolysis of the chloro and bromo complexes were monitored spectrophotometrically using a Gilford 2400S spectrophotometer interfaced with an Apple 2e computer for data collection and analysis. Reactions were monitored at 480 nm for the chloro complex and 560 nm for the bromo-derivative. An absorbance increase was observed with the chloro complex and an absorbance decrease with the bromo-derivative at these wavelengths. Base hydrolysis was very rapid and reactions were studied using succinate buffers with $\text{pH} < 6$. The hydroxide ion concentrations were derived from the pH using tabulated values of $\text{p}K_w^{12}$ and activity coefficients calculated from the Davies' equation¹³, thus at 25°, $\text{p}K_w = 13.9965$ and the activity coefficient = 0.772. All the kinetic

measurements were carried out at an ionic strength of 0.1 M.

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